

Supporting Information

Assimilating Size Diversity: Population Balance Equations Applied to the Modeling of Microplastic Transport

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Tidal boundary condition

Table S1. Tidal harmonic constituents used at the downstream sea boundary of the schematised estuary

Harmonic constituents	Amplitude [m]	Phase	Frequency [s ⁻¹]
M ₂	$A_{M_2} = 1.89$	$\phi_{M_2} = 0.0$	$f_{M_2} = 2 \pi / (3600 * 12.42) = 1.405e-4$
M ₄	$A_{M_4} = 0.15$	$\phi_{M_4} = -1.3 \pi / 180 = 2.27e-2$	$f_{M_4} = 2 f_{M_2}$
S ₂	$A_{S_2} = 0.466 * A_{M_2}$	$\phi_{S_2} = 0.0$	$f_{S_2} = 2 \pi / (3600 * 12) = 1.454e-4$

The equation used for calculation of the free surface elevation (S):

$$S = A_{M_2} \cos(f_{M_2} t + \phi_{M_2}) + A_{M_4} \cos(f_{M_4} t + \phi_{M_4}) + A_{S_2} \cos(f_{S_2} t + \phi_{S_2}) \quad (S1)$$

where t is the model simulation time.

Model parameters

Table S2. List of TELEMAC model parameters and their values for the schematised estuary model

TELEMAC Parameter	Value
TELEMAC version	v8p4r0
Simulation timestep	15 seconds
Initial water elevation	1.91 m
Bottom friction law	Chezy's law Friction coefficient = 60.0
Turbulence model	Smagorinski model
Coefficient of diffusion	1.0e-6 m ² /s
Option for the treatment of tidal flats	1: The tidal flats are detected and the free surface gradient is corrected
Treatment of negative depths	2: Flux limitation
Scheme for advection of velocities	1: Characteristic method
Scheme option for advection of velocities	1: Explicit scheme
Scheme for advection of tracers	14 : Edge by edge implementation of scheme N distributive scheme (will work on tidal flats)
Scheme option for advection of tracers	4: locally semi-implicit predictor-corrector scheme (LIPS)

Table S3. List of GAIA model parameters and their values for the schematised estuary model

GAIA Parameter	Value
DC model - settling velocities (w_{p_i}) and prescribed mass concentrations (C_i) at the river boundary	100 μm : 6.47e-4 m/s, 5.82e-07 kg/m ³ 500 μm : 1.07e-2 m/s, 2.93e-05 kg/m ³ 750 μm : 1.92e-2 m/s, 4.70e-05 kg/m ³ 1000 μm : 2.78e-2 m/s, 6.66e-05 kg/m ³ 2000 μm : 6.00e-2 m/s, 9.07e-05 kg/m ³ 5000 μm : 1.30e-1 m/s, 2.22e-04 kg/m ³
PBE model - prescribed moment concentrations (M_k) at the river boundary	M_0 : 5.15e-01 -/m ³ M_1 : 3.58e-04 m/m ³ M_2 : 8.29e-07 m ² /m ³
Plastic density (ρ_p)	1131.0 kg/m ³
Bed evolution	No
Critical shear stress for deposition	0.018 N/m ²
Solver for diffusion of suspension	1 : Conjugate gradient
Accuracy for diffusion of suspension	1.e-12

Specifications of the computing system

Table S4. Hardware and software specifications used for the model simulations

Hardware Specifications:
Processor: AMD Ryzen 7 PRO 4750U with Radeon Graphics, 1700 Mhz, 8 cores, 16 logical processors
RAM: 16 GB (Installed physical memory)
Software Environment:
Operating System: Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS (GNU/Linux 5.15.133.1-microsoft-standard-WSL2 x86_64)
Programming Language: FORTRAN 2003

Integration methods

Trapezoidal integration method

$$\int_a^b f(\xi) d\xi \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{f(\xi_{i-1}) + f(\xi_i)}{2} \Delta\xi_i \quad (\text{S2})$$

with ξ_i ranging from 1 μm to 8 mm, spaced logarithmically.

The Gauss-Hermite Quadrature method

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} f(x) dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_i f(x_i) \tag{S3}$$

where w_i are the weights and x_i are the abscissas. In the present work, 5 weight and abscissa values are chosen as follows:

$$w_i = [1.99532416e-2, 0.393619329, 0.945308745, 0.393619329, 1.99532416e-2]$$

$$x_i = [2.02018285, 0.958572447, -2.86985925e-42, -0.958572447, -2.02018285]$$

Additional plots

Figure S1. The concentration values of the 7 size classes from the DC model. The values are shown for the cross-sections at 10, 15 and 20 km.